

The Comparison of Competitiveness of Selected countries of the European Economic Area

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Abstract : The concept of competitiveness is currently very frequently used term. However, the interpretation of its essence is different. In this paper, one of the many concepts of competitiveness will be analyzed and that is macroeconomic competitiveness, which is understood as a process, which is based on the productivity growth through the growth of key macroeconomic indicators such as standards of living and employment, where all of these variables must have a sustainable basis. Given the competition is a relative quantity it must be constantly compared with the development of competitiveness in other economies or regions. And this comparison method is also used in the article that compares the macro-competitiveness of selected economies of the European Economic Area - the Czech Republic, Poland, Austria, Switzerland and Germany. The aim of the paper is to verify the hypothesis concerning the direct correlation between the size of the economy and its competitiveness.

Keywords : comparison, competitiveness, European economic area, global competitiveness index, immeasurable indicators of competitiveness, macro-competitiveness

Conference Title : ICAEBM 2014 : International Conference on Applied Economics, Business and Management

Conference Location : London, United Kingdom

Conference Dates : May 26-27, 2014